

Smart and Innovative Solutions for Maximizing Public Transport Ridership and Passengers' Satisfaction: Case Study of the City of Žilina

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Abstract. Public transport and shared mobility services are widely acknowledged as the backbone of sustainable urban transportation in terms of reduction of traffic congestion, air pollution and noise and increasing traffic safety. These services play pivotal roles in achieving the objectives of EU Cities Mission and the European Green Deal ambition of net zero greenhouse gas emission by 2050.

Alongside this, the evolution of emerging mobility concepts is also transforming the future of mobility landscape, which impose a paradigm shift towards smarter carbon-neutral mobility services. Therefore, development of smart sustainable mobility solutions and ensuring improvement of customized mobility services for all citizens are key challenges for the cities of tomorrow. All of these require experimentation besides nudging people's mobility behavior towards sustainable and climate-friendly choice of transport modes especially in Central and East European cities with high tendency for car ownership and use of private car for daily commuting.

With a twofold objective of raising public transport ridership and passengers' level of satisfaction with collective and public transport systems, this paper focuses on presenting various mobility-related solutions and measures and the implementation of the most promising ones through utilizing co-creation process for improvement of public transport service features and their smart integration with existing shared mobility services. The case study is provided for the city of Žilina as one of the twinning cities in the Horizon Europe SPINE "Smart Public transport Initiatives for Climate-Neutral cities in Europe" Innovation Action project.

Keywords: Public transport · passengers' satisfaction · awareness raising · co-creation · smart parking management · travel pattern change

1 Introduction

Increasing the use of public transport is essential for reducing traffic congestion, improving air quality, and promoting sustainable urban development. In recent decades, multitudinous methods and measures (objective and subjective) to encourage people to opt

for public transport (PT) while nudging behavior change in favor of PT and uptake of shared mobility services as a promising solution for sustainable and carbon-natural urban development have been studied in diverse contexts [1]. Thus, achieving the objective of maximizing PT ridership and making PT a viable choice for travelers requires a multi-faceted approach that focuses on improving the overall user experience and satisfaction [2–4]. In this vein, combining and utilizing various strategies and smart and people-centric solutions would catalyze cities and regions capacities to effectively increase the use of PT and ensure travelers satisfaction, leading to a more sustainable and efficient transportation system. Hence, the main objective of this paper is presenting various mobility-related solutions and measures and the implementation of the most promising ones through utilizing co-creation process for improvement of PT service features and their smart integration with existing shared mobility services in the city of Žilina as one of twinning cities in the Horizon Europe SPINE project.

The remainder of this paper is divided as follows. Section 2 presents the SPINE methodology which will be employed in the SPINE living labs (LLs). SPINE digital solutions as nudge interventions for behavioral change among trip makers towards more use of PT and shared mobility services in Žilina are presented in Sect. 3. Conclusion together with some expected impacts are addressed in Sect. 4.

2 SPINE Methodology

SPINE develops and applies an equity centered design thinking approach that spans across all its steps, starting with empathizing with the users of the solutions, proceeding to defining the plausible set of solutions, collectively co-creating and refining the solutions, implementing them, testing and assessing their impact and finally amplifying successful solutions to cities across Europe. All solutions (push and pull measures), are centered around improving the offer of PT system, addressing the diverse needs of existing and potential PT users, concentrating, and emphasizing on axes such as equity, accessibility, affordability, and inclusiveness. At the same time, a diverse multitude of co-creators (e.g., citizens, vulnerable groups, decision-makers, transport sector stakeholders, urban planners, local influencers and ambassadors) is assembled in order to acknowledge the existing condition in the local contexts, come to terms with existing barriers and potential personal biases and identify key drivers to overcome them.

3 SPINE Digital Enablers for Triggering Behavior Change in Favor of Public Transport in Žilina

City of Žilina is the fourth largest city of Slovakia with an approximate population of 85,000 inhabitants. It is an important industrial hub and transport corridor in Slovakia; therefore, it regularly faces traffic congestion and all the detrimental impacts associated with it. Although Žilina public transport is a cornerstone of urban transport system, private cars still have a high share in the city and region's modal split mostly for daily commuting to Žilina for work and education. As such, the city of Žilina as a twinning city in the SPINE project strive to unlock the true potential of PT system for increasing

its share by 30% compared to the baseline and users' satisfaction by 25% considering the needs of diverse user groups in the years of 2023 to 2027. To do so, an ambitious implementation plan has been set for the co-design, development and deployment of push and pull measures. Furthermore, integration of smart solutions and utilizing the co-creation efforts within the Žilina LL has been envisaged to reinforce existing PT offerings and integrate them with new smart mobility services which will increase users' satisfaction and will eventually contribute to the achievement of the modal shift and decarbonization targets. It is pertinent to note that for the successive learning regarding inclusive user-centered design of measures and accelerating uptake of offered solutions, the city of Žilina will also take the advantage of SPINE collaborative network of LLs fostering transferability and replicability of gained knowledge and experience across lead and twinning cities horizontally ("cross-pollination" activities) and vertically from lead city to twin cities ("twinning" activities). The implementation progress and the impact of all envisaged solutions for the city of Žilina as described in the following sections will be measured and monitored using a set of 7 predefined key performance indicators: *modal share, PT ridership, users' satisfaction, access to mobility services, congestion, air pollution and noise pollution*.

3.1 Real-Time Information for Public Transport Riders

Digitalization has become a pervasive strategy for the cost-effective management of services by public authorities while neglecting sometimes the mobility needs of non-digital travelers, people with low digital skills and city visitors and tourists. Given the fact that accurate, timely passenger information is crucial for enhancing passengers' satisfaction with PT services, this solution is aiming at accelerating the equity among all social groups and boosting passenger satisfaction in regard with providing the real time information of bus schedules (e.g. arrivals, delay), service disruptions and occupancy levels.

Real-time information for PT passengers displayed on digital screens as a relatively simple technical solution is expected to contribute to making PT more attractive for various social groups through changing citizens perception of four fundamental operational features of PT services: reliability, short waiting time, speed, and capacity [5–7], nudging green travel choice and making more informed decisions [8]. As a part of this solution, digital screens will be installed in areas with various land-use in Žilina: main PT hubs (i.e., places with significant commuter traffic where passengers can exchange between different PT lines), main hall of rail-way station and shopping malls with high travel demand. To monitor progress and the opportunities brought by this solution, the collected data on delay and passengers' occupancy together with results from the conducted quantitative and qualitative satisfaction surveys will be processed and analyzed to further explore the required areas of intervention besides the factors influencing PT users' level of satisfaction and travel experience.

3.2 Multimodal Journey Planner

Multimodal journey planners with comprehensive door-to-door information received from sensors and PT onboarding data loggers also proven a substantial impact as a digital

enabler on travel modal shift and increasing PT patrons' perception of seamless journey in particular coping with the first mile/last mile issues, usually faced by commuters from the sub-urban areas [9]. The multimodal journey planner proposed in SPINE project is an integrated, dynamic journey planner which provides the passenger with real-time and scheduled information for several mobility services (PT, sharing modes, micro-mobility, etc.) incorporating multimodal routing and optimal travel planning. Utilizing dynamic vehicle routing for on-demand mobility and real-time traffic information, the journey planner ensures that passengers can make informed decisions for their travel routes, while creating a seamless and efficient mobility experience, and optimizing the travel process. The planner will be designed to respond to user requests for a route by presenting a curated list of routes, considering factors such as quantified CO₂ emission (carbon saving) compared to car, fastest, cheapest and more suitable options. In addition, the multimodal journey planner customizes its suggestions to meet the unique needs of each traveler by analyzing user preferences and behavioral clustering. The Žilina multimodal journey planner is expected to further incentivize citizens to use PT for their entire journey, reduce traffic congestion in the central area of city and most importantly increase the use of PT through unleashing the potential of Bike & Ride as a complementary relationship between bike-sharing and public transport [10] that enables passengers to use sharing bikes in conjunction with PT system for first and last mile access in a journey.

3.3 Smart Parking Management and Low Emission Zone Action Plan

Implementing a novel smart parking management system in urban areas with mixed land-uses can significantly enhance the parking experience for users of private cars (e.g., travel time and cost reduction), reduce traffic congestion in the urban road network, and contribute to a more sustainable and efficient urban environment. On the other hand, integrating smart parking management with other modes of transportation, such as PT and bike-sharing systems using multimodal journey planner will promote seamless connections and multimodal travel between different transportation options comparing the cost, travel time and level of CO₂ emission of each transport offer for the selected trip destination to encourage people choose sustainable and efficient ways of reaching commercial areas located in the Žilina city center.

To augment the adaptation of the new measures in parking management policy, a low emission zone (LEZ) feasibility study will also be carried out in the 2nd city circuit (broader city center) close to the smart parking management implementation area. The environmental impact assessment of the LEZ study as a complementary part of smart parking management, would play an essential role in preparation of a strategic document for triggering behavior change in favor of PT and bike-sharing services. This multifaceted solution is expected to contribute to changing people's travel behavior towards multimodal trips and more use of PT and bike-sharing services in the central area of the city.

3.4 Smart City Platform for Transport and Mobility Planning

The SPINE smart city platform (SCP) as a Software as a Service (SaaS) is aimed to build and implement sustainable and resilient mobility concepts and strategies, as well

as manage their operations and assets, through the combination of big data and predictive analytics. Žilina smart city platform will be comprising of a simulation engine and tools for testing SPINE innovations, assessing their impact using quantitative key performance indicators (KPIs) and launching open-dialogue digital hub (i.e., platform for enabling participants to respond to specific solution/s and new mobility services, comment on each other posts and engage in group discussions). A stakeholders' dashboard will also provide the city authorities, policymakers, and transport operators with a series of interactive screens with the main goal of monitoring the deployed innovative solutions and monitoring the impact of combined push/pull measures. It is important to note that the SCP itself does not directly contribute to increasing passenger satisfaction or increasing the number of PT passengers. While it is supposed to increase the city's capacity by gaining a better overview of the situation in different transport sections with major implications such as contributing to more data-driven decision making and strategic planning, for an increase in PT ridership. In short, the expected output of the Žilina SCP will be a data integration space and a web-based platform providing a set of different functionalities and dashboards (e.g., goal view, modules view, KPIs and analytics view). This tool will allow the city authorities to efficiently monitor the SPINE-related mobility measures through 4 sets of identified KPIs for the city of Žilina: *I) PT quality of services* (e.g. Ridership volume, Passengers' satisfaction, Travel time reliability and Accessibility), *II) On-street parking management* (e.g. Parking capacity and Parking search time), *III) Traffic information* (e.g. Modal share and Congestion indexes) and *IV) Environmental impact* (e.g. Air pollution and Noise pollution levels).

3.5 Rebranding Public Transport Campaigns

To raise awareness and emphasize on the environmental benefits of using PT, among diverse social group of people, a series of pop-up exhibition supported by city of Žilina, Žilina public transport company and other relevant stakeholders will be organized. The main aim of the pop-up exhibitions is to encourage critical thinking among participants, observe the interactions of the participants with the various displays of open questions and proposed solutions and to gather quantitative and qualitative data focused on key drivers of modal shift to PT and satisfaction from PT services and other shared mobility services [11]. To further foster the communication between the city and citizens, promote the mobility solutions and push and pull measures, the SPINE Citizens App will be also developed within the project. The Citizens App will serve as a citizens engagement platform with features such as travel logging, offering tailored incentives per user group based on user preferences, previous experience. Incentives, offers, and promotions will also be discussed and presented during the Living Lab (LL) and pop-up exhibitions organized in Žilina.

4 Conclusion

Public transport system is the robust and collective backbone of urban mobility, playing the central role in the desired future of transportation. Considering that most European major cities are undergoing to experience urban population growth by 2030, hereupon

urbanization trend is envisaged to resonate demands for smart technology initiatives to make PT more appealing and accommodate seamless and inclusive mobility needs of citizens. Therefore, the co-designed technological and non-technological mobility solutions jointly developed in the cities' LLs would empower transportation systems to become resilient and able to deal with exceptional situations. The proposed measures, thanks to deployment of design thinking and co-creation methods, are expected to unlock opportunities in the city of Žilina by bringing together public and private interests in the evolution of PT and sustainable and green mobility leading to an increase of the share of PT ridership by approximately 30% and the user satisfaction with PT by 25% compared to the baseline, and cover different market/customer segments providing a better social inclusion and healthier lifestyles. In conclusion, it is essential to acknowledge the inherent limitations posed by the absence of primary data. The forthcoming research will be dedicated to collecting quantitative and qualitative data that will enable us to enhance the depth and breadth of our analysis, leading to more robust conclusions and practical implications. This study serves as a steppingstone toward a more comprehensive understanding of digital enablers' role for triggering behavior change in favor of PT and its implications.

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References

1. Rasca, S., Saeed, N.: Exploring the factors influencing the use of public transport by commuters living in networks of small cities and towns. *Travel Behav. Soc.* **28**, 249–263 (2022)
2. Walker, J.: *Human transit: How clearer thinking about public transit can enrich our communities and our lives*. Island Press, Washington, D.C. (2012)
3. Brakewood, C., Macfarlane, G.S., Watkins, K.: The impact of real-time information on bus ridership in New York City. *Transp. Res. Part C Emerg. Technol.* **53**, 59–75 (2015)
4. Lunke, E.B.: Commuters' satisfaction with public transport. *J. Transp. Health* **16**, 100842 (2020)
5. Watkins, K.E., Ferris, B., Borning, A., Rutherford, G.S., Layton, D.: Where is my bus? Impact of mobile real-time information on the perceived and actual wait time of transit riders. *Transp. Res. Part A Policy Pract.* **45**(8), 839–848 (2011)
6. Redman, L., Friman, M., Gärling, T., Hartig, T.: Quality attributes of public transport that attract car users: a research review. *Transp. Policy* **25**, 119–127 (2013)
7. Soza-Parra, J., Raveau, S., Muñoz, J.C., Cats, O.: The underlying effect of public transport reliability on users' satisfaction. *Transp. Res. Part A Policy Pract.* **126**, 83–93 (2019)
8. Maclean, S., Dailey, D.: Measuring the utility of a real-time transit information system. In: *Proceedings the IEEE 5th International Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, pp. 846–850 (2002)
9. Reed, T., Biermann, S.: *Journey planner usage analysis. Final Report, iMOVE Project*, Planning and Transport Research Centre, University of Western Australia (2020)
10. Martens, K.: The bicycle as a feeder mode: experiences from three European countries. *Transp. Res. Part D: Transp. Environ.* **9**(4), 281–294 (2004)

11. Pourhashem, G., Malichova, E., Kováčiková, T.: The role of participation behavior and information in nudging citizens sustainable mobility behavior: a case study of Bratislava region. In: 19th International Conference on Emerging eLearning Technologies and Applications (ICETA) Proceeding, Košice, Slovakia, pp. 300–306. IEEE (2021)

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